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RESEARCH ANALYSIS IN CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR OF AUTOMOBILE PASSENGER CAR CUSTOMERS IN COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT

The car business today is the most lucrative industry. Because of increment in discretionary cash flow in both country and urban part and accessibility of simple fund are the primary drivers of high volume auto sectors. Assist rivalry is warming up with host of new players coming in and worldwide brands like Porsche, Bentley, and Ferrari all set to wander in Indian market. This examination will be useful for the current and new participant auto fabricating organizations in India to discover the client desires and their market offerings. Coimbatore auto business is impacted by the presence of numerous national and multinational car makers. This paper presents investigation of research in the zone of Consumer Behaviour of Automobile Car Customer at the geographical coverage of Coimbatore. Appropriate comprehension of buyer purchasing conduct will help the advertiser to prevail in the market. All fragments in Coimbatore urban car industry were examined and found that purchaser has diverse need of practices in every section, where as fundamental driver for auto buy is extra cash. Esteem for cash, wellbeing and driving solaces best the rank regarding client necessity; though saw quality by clients chiefly relies on upon brand picture. For this examination, strategy received was to concentrate the exploration papers in the region of Passenger Car fragment, concentrate the buy choice process and its connection with conduct parameters over every one of the portions of auto, for example, little and Hatch Back section, Sedan class portion, SUV and MUV portion and Luxury Car portion. The goal of this review is the ID of elements impacting client's inclinations for specific fragment of autos. This paper likewise endeavours to combine discoveries and proposals to conquer display situation of stagnancy in deals and develop future interest for car auto showcase.

Key Words: Consumer behaviour, Small Car, Sedan, Customer Perception, Luxury Car segment, Automobile Industry

INTRODUCTION

India being the second most populated country in the world and the growth rate of Indian economy is also high as compared to developed countries, which attracts the presence of huge demand in the Automobile Small Car Industry. Coimbatore is becoming emerging market for worldwide auto giants. Coimbatore is on growth path and has highest passenger vehicle penetration.

There are various reasons for the growth of the Coimbatore automobile market such as -

1. The people have more disposable income as economy is growing.
2. Increase in the need of mobility due to urbanization and leisure travel.
3. Car Finance options available from Financial Institutes at reasonable rate of interest.
4. Availability of service centres and spare parts in near vicinity.
5. Improvement in highway infrastructure.

For a large portion of the general population, acquiring an auto is the second most essential and costly choice, beside buy of a house; for the car makers, first-time auto purchasers give them the chance to make positive brand picture which unquestionably could be reflected in next coming years since shoppers could make rehash auto buying. The idea of "purchasing conduct" is of prime significance in promoting and has advanced throughout the years. It is essential to comprehend purchaser purchasing conduct as it assumes a fundamental

part while buying items. Everyday human needs are developing, desire is developing. Auto Models are no special case to this conduct. Shopper conduct is genuinely perplexing as Auto Buy infers an abnormal state of social and mental inclusion. Shopper purchasing conduct is a mix of Monetary, innovative, political, social, statistic and common components and additionally Client's own qualities which is reflected by his mentality, inspiration, recognition, identity, learning and way of life. This prompt to consistent adjustments of Auto Models and its elements as far as their size, limit, styling and so forth and today we see another model coming into the market for all intents and purposes each quarter. Advertise has turned out to be extremely focused and has turned out to be exceptionally 'essential place' to concentrate the conduct of buyers furthermore give helpful bits of knowledge what a purchaser requires in an item in a steady element environment. Buyer conduct additionally contrasts for same Auto under beneath conditions-New Car launch in market

1. Car is in market for 1-2 years
2. Car is in the market for more than 4 years
3. Purchase of second hand Car

It is just through research that an organization will have the capacity to concentrate the purchasing conduct of customers. With better comprehension of client's recognitions, organizations can decide the activities required to address the client's issue. They can recognize their own qualities and shortcomings, where they remain in contrast with their rivals, diagram the future advance way and change. The traveller auto advertise changed quickly because of the wild rivalry and propel innovation, along these lines, it requires the car produces to comprehend the customer's inclination on time and take quick activities to reflect showcase changes rapidly. So it would be extremely intriguing to know buyer's inclination in today's quick changing traveller auto market and how is the client's purchasing procedure.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Because of the rise of globalization and advancement there is a solid fulfilment among the Vehicle ventures which are centring consideration in catching the Indian markets a car are not any more considered as extravagance once, now involves a piece of everyday life and has turned into a need. Clients have now changed their disposition that yesterday's extravagances are today's necessities. To be a fruitful advertiser it is significant to concentrate the view of the planned purchasers and track their drivers of those discernments.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Manish Kumar Srivastava, A.K. Tiwari, studies the consumer behavior for A3 segment vehicles such as Honda City and SX4 in a particular region Jaipur. Data collected from 100 respondents 50 each from Honda City and Maruti SX4. Respondents were considered from various backgrounds like Gender, Occupation, Income class. Also customer purchase parameters considered for study are Price, Safety, Comfort, Power & Pickup, Mileage, Max Speed, Styling, After Sales Service, Brand Name and Spare Parts Cost. Based on above parameters and analysis made in this it revealed that, while purchasing A3 segment car Customer give much importance to Safty, Brand Name and seating and driving comfort. Also word of mouth publicity and advertisements in car magazines are more effective communication medium for promotion of Cars.
2. Prasanna Mohan Raj, studied the factors influencing customers brand preference of the economy segment SUV's and MUV's. Data collection was made through direct interaction and customer intercept survey using questionnaire. Descriptive analysis was used to transform data into understand format and factor analysis was used for identification of factors influencing customer preference. In light of study findings, the preference of a given brand can be explained in terms of six factors namely Product reliability, monetary factor, trendy appeal, frequency of non-price promotions offered, trustworthiness and customer feeling or association towards brand. There is need for marketers to take these factors into consideration when crafting product innovations in the SUV segment of Automobile market.
3. Nikhil Monga, Bhuvender Chaudhary, Saurabh Tripathi, this research attempts to answer some of the questions regarding brand personality of selected cars in India by conducting the market research. This personality sketching will help in knowing what a customer (or a potential customer) thinks

about a given brand of car and what are the possible factors guiding a possible purchase. Similarly, the idea of measuring the customer satisfaction will serve the same purpose of determining the customer perception. Thus, by measuring the willingness of exciting users of a car to recommend it to others will help the car manufacturers to check out the entire customer Buying Behavior. The study shows that brand perception is something which starts building up before a car is purchased and goes on with its use and is reflected in the recommendations. The customer makes to his acquaintances for the same car. Also it is seen that the customer might not be using the car still he holds the perceptions about it. Brand personality of a car is enforced by the sellers in the mindsets of the customers and customers reacts to it by forming their perception about the car and this reflects in the overall brand image of the car. So brand image and brand personality complement each other and the brand perception aids the building of brand images. As per the study findings, dealers play a very important role in building up the brand perceptions of the cars.

4. Samin Rezvani, Goodarz Javadian Dehkordi, Muhammad Sabbir Rahman, this paper reviews the country of origin and different variables that influence consumer purchase intention, also highlight the relationship of variables and customer purchase intention. Study demonstrate that people care about which country products come from and where they are made and consider these factors when evaluating the quality of product. Stereotypes of country and the preferences of customers, influence the purpose intention. Political system, culture and the economy of the country can be a cause of sensitivity to people. There are many factors that have an impact on consumer purchase intention. Research and methodologies have shown that even when consumers can evaluate all the intrinsic product characteristics by expressing the product, the effect of extrinsic cues has more influence on consumer product evaluation. Country of origin is one of the extrinsic cues; in addition, there is no doubt that country of origin has considerable influence on the purchase intention process.
5. K.Vidyavathi, the study throws light on various aspects that the manufactures should concentrate on to attract the prospective buyers. The demand for the small Automobile segment is increasing because of the growing number of nuclear families as well as parking problems. Hence the manufactures should find out the needs, wants, tastes and preferences of consumers in order to design the products. Also fuel economy and driving comfort are the most important parameters followed by availability of spares and their price.
6. Balakrishnan Menon, Jagathy Raj V.P., study findings shows that due to price difference in Gasoline and Diesel, about one third of the car owners were having diesel vehicles. The research results showed that about one seventh of car for the city drive for family usage, while using the second car for office and business usage. Foreign brand cars show clear preference in the Kerala car market. Also it was observed that in the information gathering and consumer purchase initiation stage, TV commercials on car models and brands, search on internet website of the manufacturer and visit to dealers / distributors were the prime sources where customers gathers information on car models.
7. Ramita Verma, Shubhkamana Rathore , studied the luxury car segment of India. Researches and studies have revealed that the luxury car market is growing at a steady speed of 25% per annum with more and more numbers of luxury cars entering Indian car market. Luxury cars are preferred by HNI (High Net worth Individuals). HNI wants to differentiate themselves from crowd for various reasons. Change in attitude of the customer accounts for the sudden acceleration in the Luxury car Market in India, as the emphasis has been shifted from price consideration and affordability to design, quality and pleasure. Study also throws light on market drivers of luxury cars like
 - Political-government tax collection, business conclusions, import-trade approaches, government solidness.
 - Demographical components like Consumer patterns, Income development, spending power.
 - Customer necessities, for example, grown-up toy, liberality, innovative components.
 - Socio social elements, for example, Lifestyle and inclinations of individuals which affect their selection of sorts of autos. Social standards that effect the choice to claim and utilize vehicles versus different method for transport.

METHODOLOGY

However every one of the reviews made in Consumer purchasing conduct of Automotive Car for different fragments from little up to extravagance auto gives the skill to Car Manufacturer yet neglects to give logical way to deal with variables of Consumer conduct and their drivers. In this paper an endeavour is made to-

1. Study & Classify Car market based on segments like – small car, Hatch back, Sedan Class, premium Sedan, SUV & MUV and Luxury Car.
2. Study on purchase decision process.
3. Broad classification of behaviours and their effect on various car segments.

Coimbatore Car Market Segments:

Coimbatore auto industry is currently the fifteenth biggest among Indian urban cities. The general Indian car industry has developed at a high rate of around 15% (CAGR 2007-12) on the back of a sound full scale financial development and general positive assumptions. As India is a creating economy with generally low GDP per capita, the Indian car industry is overwhelmed by 2-Wheelers which contain ~77% of the general market. Passenger vehicles are the second biggest fragment of the business with a share of ~15% and business and three wheelers involve 8% of the piece of the pie. In India Passenger Vehicle market is further characterized into three sections

- Passenger Cars (PC)
- Utility Vehicles (UV)
- Vans (Mini Vans - not included in study)

Passenger Cars sub-segment dominates the passenger vehicle market in India with ~70% share. The next biggest sub-segment is the Utility Vehicles segment which has a share of ~20%, followed by Mini Vans.

Passenger Car Segment:

The Passenger Car (PC) segment is categorized into 9 sub-segments primarily based on overall vehicle length

- Micro
- Mini
- Compact
- Super compact
- Mid size
- Executive
- Premium
- Luxury
- Coupe

Out of the 9 sub-fragments, 3 sub-portions viz. Conservative, Mini and Super Compact include ~90% of the general traveler auto (PC) showcase. The biggest sub-fragment is Compact trailed by Mini. The interest for little autos is the most astounding in view of generally lower per-capita salaries and high movement thickness in urban zones. Smaller and Mini sub-portions fundamentally include hatchbacks which are favored because of moderately low value, high fuel productivity and simple mobility. Suzuki is the main player in the traveler auto section with a prevailing offer of ~45%, indirectly took after by Hyundai with a share of ~20%.

Purchase Decision Process:

In order to assess the importance of the environmental awareness in the car purchase decision, it is necessary to get an insight into the process of purchasing itself. The consumer's decision to purchase a product is a multi staged process. Kotler (2006) identifies that the consumer will go through five stages. Vehicle purchase behavior fairly complex, as car purchase implies a high level of social and / or psychological involvement. Therefore, the consumer will transit each stage of purchase decision making process as presented in figure-1.

Figure 1: The Purchase Decision Making Process (Source – Kotler)

- a) **Problem Recognition:** In this information processing model, the consumer buying process begins when the buyer recognizes a problem or need. When we found out a difference between the actual state and a desired state, a problem is recognized. When we find a problem, we usually try to solve the problem. We, in other words, recognize the need to solve the problem. But how?
- b) **Information Search:** When a consumer discovers a problem, he/she is likely to search for more information. Through gathering information, the consumer learns more about some brands that compete in the market and their features and characteristics.
- c) **Evaluation and Selection of Alternatives:** How does the consumer process competitive brand information and evaluate the value of the brands? Unfortunately there is no single, simple evaluation process applied by all consumers or by one consumer in all buying situations. One dominant view, however, is to see the evaluation process as being cognitively driven and rational. Under this view, a consumer is trying to solve the problem and ultimately satisfying his/her need. In other words, he/she will look for problem-solving benefits from the product. The consumer, then, looks for products with a certain set of attributes that deliver the benefits. Thus, the consumer sees each product as a bundle of attributes with different levels of ability of delivering the problem solving benefits to satisfy his/her need. The distinctions among the need, benefits, and attributes are very important. One useful way to organize the relationships among the three is a hierarchical one.
- d) **Decision Implementation:** To actually implement the purchase decision, however, a consumer needs to select both specific items (brands) and specific outlets (where to buy) to resolve the problems. There are, in fact, three ways these decisions can be made: 1) simultaneously; 2) item first, outlet second; or 3) outlet first, item second. In many situations, consumers engage in a simultaneous selection process of stores and brands. Once the brand and outlet have been decided, the consumer moves on to the transaction.

Post-purchase Evaluation: Post-purchase evaluation processes are directly influenced by the type of preceding decision-making process. Directly relevant here is the level of purchase involvement of the consumer. Purchase involvement is often referred to as “the level of concern for or interest in the purchase” situation, and it determines how extensively the consumer searches information in making a purchase decision. Although purchase involvement is viewed as a continuum (from low to high), it is useful to consider two extreme cases here. Suppose one buys a certain brand of product as a matter of habit (habitual purchase). For him/her, buying a is a very low purchase involvement situation, and he/she is not likely to search and evaluate product information extensively. In such a case, the consumer would simply purchase, consume and/or dispose of the product with very limited post-purchase evaluation and generally maintain a high level of repeat purchase motivation.

4.3 Broad Classification of consumer behaviour:

Consumer behavior is a blend of Economic, Technological, Political, Cultural, Demographic and natural factors as well as his own characteristics which is reflected by his attitude, motivation, perception, personality, knowledge and lifestyle. Marketers can rationalize their existence only when they are able to understand consumer behavior. From study it was envisaged to classify these behavior parameters under broad categories – Economic, Social, Demographic, Geographic, Psychological, Product & Technology. Various customer behavior parameters can be clubbed as given in below Figure 2.

Figure: 2 Classification of Consumer Behaviour

Based on the analysis and as shown in figure 3, it is evident that, increase in disposable income seems to be the most important reason for buying a car. This trend is reflected in the growth of the per capita income and consequently the growth of the Indian automobile Industry. Similarly, the growing family needs like working partners, increasing family size, status, etc. add to the motives of buying a car. At the same time affordability of car price is the most important factors for purchasing a particular segment car.

Figure 3: Drivers for Buying a Car.

Customer Behaviours of various Passenger Car segments are as described below:

Micro Car Segment: It is the lowest cost segment with only one Tata Nano Car. Despite being the cheapest car, had serious initial quality issues which damaged its brand image and customer faith. As a product this segment will get preference for city drive over congested road conditions wherein safety on road will be better than two-wheeler.

Mini Car Segment: It is the 2nd largest sub-segment in the passenger car market is highly consolidated with 2~3 significant players having 7 products. The reason for presence of relatively few players in this segment is because of highly price sensitive consumer. To enable competitive low cost manufacturing, high volumes and thus a large network is required. Maruti Suzuki and Hyundai are the dominant players in the sub-segment as they were the early entrants and have low cost manufacturing competence. Consumers of these segment cars are 1st time car buyers with product price as deciding factor. M800, Suzuki Alto, Zen, Wagon R, Santro, Spark are the cars from this segment.

Compact car segment: It is the most crowded segment with about 13 players and 20 product offerings as it is the largest sub-segment (~45% share) in passenger cars. Yet, the ability to manufacture low cost good quality cars has resulted in the market being relatively consolidated with 2 players – Maruti Suzuki and Hyundai – dominating the market with a combined share of over 50%. While Maruti Suzuki, Hyundai and Tata were the early entrants in the sub-segment, Honda has already overtaken Tata to become the 3rd largest player in the sub-segment. This has happened because of high brand equity and competitive pricing of Honda products. Swift, i10, Jazz, Vista, Beat, Figo, Polo, Micra, Liva, Vibe, Punto, Pulse etc. are the cars from this segment.

Super Compact: “Super Compact”, the largest sub-segment, is comprised of sedans and marks the beginning of 3 box cars in the segment. This sub-segment is dominated by Maruti Suzuki with cheapest sedan Swift Dzire developed on its most successful compact hatchback car platform. The dominance of Maruti Suzuki ends at this sub-segment in the hierarchy. “Mid-size” is the 4th largest sub-segment in passenger car market. It is also the relative more fragmented sub-segment with 11 players offering 14 products. Most players in this segment either offer a product which shares platform with it offering in the Compact sub-segment or a global product. Hyundai is the dominant player in this segment due to competitively priced feature-rich product with option of both gasoline and diesel powered engines.

The choice of car in this segment is driven by income. In this segment customers first preference is for safety, driving & Seating comfort and brand, second most preference is for after sales service, price, power and pickup, mileage whereas maximum speed is of lowest preference. Also this segment requires value for money, best features, and customer friendly vehicle.

Executive: Due to low sub-segment volumes, most players offer global products which are manufactured using CKDs (Completely Knocked Down kits). Hyundai and Toyota are the leading players in the segment. This is an executive and premium class segment customer; most of these owners tend to have purchased a car previously, the customer has potentially developed an attitude towards car. In this segment attitude becomes an evaluating judgment based on prior or present experience. These customers preference is for attractive styling, brand image, best product performance in terms of acceleration, max speed and higher horse power. These customers seek to show personality, leadership from brand of car as most of the customers prefer this segment for business purpose. Car price, fuel efficiency, spares cost are of secondary importance. Car interiors styling such as IP shape & finish, all customer touch points, seat, steering door handle etc. are of high importance. Also exterior styling, overall look, paint finish and safety & driving comforts are of prime importance.

Luxury and Coupe sub-segment: These are relatively marginal segments with less than 1% combined share of the passenger car market. Almost all products in these sub-segments are offered through the CBU route (Completely Built Unit) due to miniscule volumes which neither justify neither localization nor local assembly. This segment is of high end luxury cars such as Audi, BMW, Jaguar, Mercedes, Lexus, Porsche, Rolls-Royce, as these brands are considered luxury. Average car price of this segment cars is more than Rs. 35 Lakh and is growing at an average rate of 20% Y-O-Y. According to the Report of World Wealth by Capgemini and Merrill Lynch Wealth Management, most countries in the world have increased their HNI (High Net-worth Individuals) count. While, India has more than doubled it – maximum compared to any other country in the world. HNI customers are celebrities, business leaders, and corporate honchos, politicians from urban and rural India. Their attitudes are “Got it? Flaunt it”, “Power Show”, “Image and Uniqueness”. High social status from perceived brand image is the common driving factor of this segment. Superior functionality, best in class quality and high end & customized features are the most preferred parameters of this segment.

SUV & MUV Segment: This segment is actually utility segment further segmented into UV1, UV2, UV3 and UV4 based on length and price parameter. Economy segment UV’s are Sumo, Safari, Aarya, Bolero, Scorpio, XUV500, Xylo, Innova. Whereas high end UV market is very limited and dominated by Fortuner, Prado, Landcruiser, Pajero etc. Customers of economy and high end SUV shows difference mainly in terms of affordability of vehicle price, spares cost and serviceability. Whereas the main driving factor of this segment is fun, road presence, egocentric relationship. In India economy class SUV’s found to be of better choice in rural area as product image is rugged, muscular, rough& tough, worthiness to bad roads. High end SUV customers are celebrities, business tycoons, politicians those want to use car as indulgence. These segment cars are having high perceived safety by customers because of looks, overall structure and exterior styling of vehicle.

SUGGESTIONS AND FINDINGS:

1. India is still subject to bay nations for its fuel necessity. Vulnerability and trustworthiness for fuel on different nations limits the development of Indian auto industry. Likewise cash utilized all inclusive for

fuel estimating is USD and any variance in coin has coordinate effect on fuel cost which hoses the auto deal. Producers need to concentrate on option fills to drive the eventual fate of auto industry.

2. Insecurity in Indian economy will immediate affect auto deal, as auto is seen as way of life item. In spite of the fact that auto industry can't be protected from the impacts of back off and retreat in economy, industry should be more in sync with development and advancement of India.
3. Growth in extra cash and advanced education will remain the primary drivers of future propel autos. Auto makers need to track these patterns and adjust their item techniques.
4. Indian and Tamil Nadu state governments ought to approach, lessen the tax assessment and update the obligation structure for green vehicles those are - less toxin, high fuel effective, safe drive vehicles. Government ought to guarantee better quality autos to be accessible on streets and actualize ELV (End of Life) standards. Autos employing on streets for over 10 years ought to be re-examined for their appropriate working and roadworthiness. Street framework should be further overhauled to bolster mechanical prerequisites, for example, ABS, Air Bag, and Vehicle following through GPS, RFID and electric auto by demonstrating street side electrical charging.
5. Car merchants and makers indicate great neighbourliness to clients amid their visits to the place of showroom before and promptly after their buy. Be that as it may, after some time they confront an issue with their merchants in regards to after deals benefit. Along these lines, it is proposed that the administrations rendered r to be rendered ought to be legitimately clarified, inviting methodology and unwavering quality in support of be further moved forward. Cost of extra parts to be charged sensibly.
6. The increment in number of ladies auto proprietors, utilizing the auto for their office, staff and family work, accordingly turning into a compelling gathering, calls for particular consideration of auto makers and advertisers to centre their vital endeavours in this course.
7. During introductory hunt, TV advertisements on auto models and brands, seek on web sites of the producer and visit to merchants/wholesalers were the prime sources where clients assembled data on auto models and brands, advertisers might need to concentrate on these elements to get the consideration of the meaning future clients.
8. When it came to choice in light of inclinations, individual needs, the top opening parameters were - the need of the business firm, peer weight from other relatives owning an auto and updated the model to suit individual aspiration. Advertisers need to comprehend these prerequisites and centre their promoting techniques towards these client necessities.
9. In the class of individual inclination on solace variables, prevailing elements were solace in driving, esteem for cash and inside plan, which beat the necessity list. Auto portion shrewd examination additionally drew out these particular solace prerequisites over every one of the brands. Producers may investigate these viewpoints to their auto configuration, so to draw in auto travellers, inclined to choose the models in view of these criteria.

CONCLUSION

Customer conduct comprises of all human conduct that goes in settling on before and post buy choices. One can prevail in the aggressive market simply subsequent to comprehension the mind boggling purchaser conduct. A comprehension of the customer empowers an advertiser to take showcasing choices which are perfect with its shopper needs. From study there are different significant class of customer conduct determinants and desires, in particular financial, mental, political, eographical, statistic and Product and Technology. Advance grouping of human practices under primary classes will empower auto producer to adjust their techniques in simultaneousness to client conduct. While acquiring small scale portion auto however client is exceedingly taken a toll cognizant yet this fragment is likewise redesigning their prerequisites and because of ascend in discretionary cashflow, with in section relocation is watched, Customer is more disposed to buy Suzuki Swift, 120. For moderate size fragment client center is for security, driving and seating solace, mark. Additionally this portion requires esteem for cash, best components and client amicable vehicles. In higher fragment autos like Executive and Premium brand picture is principle main component which gives affirmation of addressing their needs interms of security, execution and highlight necessities. Worldwide brands are exceedingly favored in Executive or more fragments. So auto organizations ought to embrace the "Think-Global, Act-Global".

Approach in system making which includes institutionalization over the world. Mark worldwide nearness is judged by purchasers in light of accessibility around the world with institutionalized items, mark name, dispersion channels and correspondences. By going worldwide, the organization will appreciate an expansion in piece of the overall industry, which demonstrates increment popular for their items. With that, the organization can deliver with economies of scale, diminish cost per unit and increment generation productivity bringing about serving clients productively and financially. Above all, contrasted with neighbourhood brands, organizations with worldwide brands will have the capacity to enter into business sectors all the more effortlessly, notwithstanding to high or low status looking for shoppers, worldwide brands with appropriate procedure will empower them to accomplish an improved worldwide picture.

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